

Geospatial Electrification Analysis for Zambia: An OnSSET Based Approach to Achieve 100% Access by 2030

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Geospatial Electrification, OnSSET, Energy Mix, Grid Extension, Mini-Grids, Solar Home Systems, Regional Interconnection, Mission 300, Least Cost Planning, Universal Access, Integrated Resource Plan, Zambia Energy Demand Stimulation Incentive, Vision 2030.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report presents a geospatial least cost electrification analysis for Zambia using the OnSSET tool. The objective was to explore suitable strategies to achieve universal electricity access by 2030, in alignment with national policy goals including the Integrated Resource Plan (IRP), the Eighth National Development Plan (8NDP) and Mission 300.

Two scenarios were explored. Scenario 1 prioritized decentralized solutions through Zambia's 1000 mini-grid initiative (ZEDSI), while Scenario 2 emphasized grid expansion and regional interconnection. Both achieved universal access by 2030, but Scenario 1 proved more cost-effective (USD 3.3 billion vs. USD 3.66 billion) and deployed over 1,100 mini-grids compared to 406 in Scenario 2.

Key recommendations include scaling up mini-grids and SHSs in remote provinces, investing in grid upgrades for densification, enhancing private sector participation and diversifying financing mechanisms. The study highlights the value of OnSSET as a spatial decision support tool and underscores the need for updated geospatial data and institutional capacity to support Zambia's electrification goals.

1. INTRODUCTION

Zambia is a landlocked country located in the heart of Southern Africa. It is home to approximately 20.8 million people with 59.2% living in rural areas and 40.8% living in urban areas. According to the National Energy Access Survey (NEAS) of 2023 conducted by the Ministry of Energy (MoE), national electricity access stood at 53.6%. Of this figure, 34% were connected to the grid while 19.6% were connect to Solar Home Systems (SHSs) and mini-grids. Furthermore, 80% of the urban population had access to electricity compared to 34% of the rural population.

1.1 Purpose and Scope

Zambia has an installed generation capacity of 3336MW. However, national access to electricity remains a challenge particularly in rural areas. Some of the challenges hindering access include, grid infrastructure limitations, financial and investment constraints, large connections fees and overdependence on Hydro generation which is vulnerable to climate change.

To address these issues, Zambia has adopted several policies and strategic frameworks aimed at achieving 100% national electricity access by 2030. These include the Zambia Energy Demand Stimulation Incentive (ZEDSI), the Eighth National Development Plan (8NDP), the Integrated Resource Plan (IRP) and Mission 300. Collectively, these initiatives target increasing generation capacity to 9000MW, upgrading and expanding existing grid network, regional interconnection and diversifying the energy mix.

1.2 Aim and Objectives

This case study seeks to investigate suitable models for Zambia to achieve universal, affordable and sustainable electricity access by 2030. This will be done by:

- Simulating various approaches to meet 100% national access
- Comparing the technology mix and investments costs involved
- Provide insights and recommendations based on modelling outputs

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Modelling Approach/Tool

The study applied a geospatial least cost electrification planning approach using the Open-Source Spatial Electrification Tool (OnSSET) model on which the Global Electrification Platform is based. OnSSET is designed to support energy planning by offering cost effective electrification strategies. It does this by comparing and evaluating investment costs on grid extension, mini-grids (PV Hybrid, Hydro & Wind) and SHS's. The model enables planners to adjust parameters such as electricity demand, technology costs, pricing structures, distance to grid infrastructure and population distribution to reflect country specific conditions.

The study also utilized QGIS, which is a Geographic Information System (GIS) software used for creating, visualizing, editing, and analyzing geospatial datasets. QGIS was essential in preparing input layers and validating outputs.

The steps undertaken during the study include:

- i. Data Collection (both GIS and non-GIS datasets)
- ii. Data Processing and preparation using QGIS
- iii. Exporting GIS data to structured CSV files compatible with OnSSET
- iv. Calibration of the OnSSET model to reflect Zambia's current electrification status and targets
- v. Running OnSSET to simulate least-cost technology allocation for universal access by 2030
- vi. Analysis and Visualization of the results.

2.2 Data sources

Layer	Source
Administrative boundaries	GADM
Medium-voltage lines (Existing)	Energy Data
Service transformers (existing)	Energy Data
Substations	OpenStreetMap
High-voltage lines (Existing)	Energy Data
Road network	OpenStreetMap
Settlement clusters	HumData
Global Horizontal Irradiation (GHI) - Solar resource	Global Solar Atlas
Small scale hydropower sites	KTH
Wind velocity (m/s)	Global Wind Atlas
Travel hours (minutes)	Malaria Atlas Project
Night-time lights	Earth Observation Group
Existing mini-grid locations	Energy Data

Custom demand layer (if bottom-up approach is included)	KTH
Location of Health Facilities (if social uses are included)	HDEx
Location of Education Institutions (if social uses are included)	HDEx

Table 1: Data layers used and their sources

2.3 Assumptions

The following assumptions were applied for both scenarios:

- Population growth: from 20.8 million in 2023 to 26 million by 2030
- Target electrification rate: 100%
- Urbanization growth: from 34 to 51%
- Number of people per urban household = 4.6
- Number of people per rural household = 5
- Grid loss rates: 15%
- This is the average emissions from grid generation = 402.9gCO₂/kWh
- Discount rates (all technologies): 12%
- Diesel price: \$1.1
- Mini-hydro priority distance = 5km

2.4 Scenarios

2.4.1 Scenario 1

The first scenario was designed to prioritize the ZEDSI programme's 1000 mini grid initiative which is a new financial mechanism designed to accelerate the deployment of mini grids by offering a grant based subsidy to mini grid developers in order to catalyze wider scale electrification across Zambia. The following calibrations were made:

- Minimum number of households in a settlement for mini-grids to be considered = 100
- Minimum distance from existing MV lines for mini-grids to be considered as an option = 0km
- Maximum share of generation that can come from diesel generators = 50%
- Maximum number of grid connections yearly = 300000
- Buffer distance (km) for automatic intensification = 0km
- Demand levels:
 - Urban areas-Tier 4 (1241 kwh/household/year)
 - Rural (large)- Tier 3 (365 kwh/household/year)
 - Rural (small)- Tier 1 (43 kwh/household/year)

2.4.2 Scenario 2

The second scenario was designed to prioritize grid expansion while balancing the deployment of mini grids. This was based on the country's target to increase generation capacity and regional interconnection as outlined in the National Energy Compact. Thus, the following calibrations were made:

-
- Minimum number of households in a settlement for mini-grids to be considered = 200
 - Minimum distance from existing MV lines for mini-grids to be considered as an option = 10km
 - Maximum share of generation that can come from diesel generators = 20%
 - Maximum number of grid connections yearly = Unlimited
 - Buffer distance (km) for automatic intensification = 10km
 - Demand levels:
 - Urban areas-Tier 4 (1241 kwh/household/year)
 - Rural (large)- Tier 3 (365 kwh/household/year)
 - Rural (small)- Tier 2 (120 kwh/household/year)

3. RESULTS

3.1 Scenario 1

	Population 2030	New Connections 2030	Capacity 2030 (MW)	Investment 2030 (million USD)	Emissions2030 (tCO2)
Grid_dens	16472336	1883095	618.09	2361.88	927.08
Grid_ext	1002933	217596	22.74	279.92	34.05
SA_PV	6249424	505399	19.64	303.13	0
MG_PV_Hybrid	2213586	311825	98.87	321.88	368.61
MG_Wind	0	0	0	0	0
MG_Hydro	61719	10979	1.95	25.87	0
Non-electrified	0	0	0	0	0
Total	25999998	2928894	761.29	3292.681	1329.74

Table 2: Results summary of Scenario 1

Key Findings

- Number of new MG PV Hybrid = 1103
- Number of new MG Hydro = 54
- Total Investment cost = \$3.3 billion

Figure 1: Technology Map for Scenario

Figure 2: Population electrification rate for Scenario 1

Scenario 1 allows a very diverse mix of energy across the country, with many mini grids being deployed in low density areas like North Western and Eastern provinces.

3.2 Scenario 2

	Population 2030	New Connections 2030	Capacity 2030 (MW)	Investment2030 (million USD)	Emissions2030 (tCO2)
Grid_dens	16472336	1883095	618.18	2362.12	927.22
Grid_ext	1662800	353325	34.38	483.27	51.13
SA_PV	6170400	488239	38.87	592.68	0
MG_PV_Hybrid	1662854	198142	79.2	207.07	281.5
MG_Wind	0	0	0	0	0
MG_Hydro	31606	6093	1.08	13.47	0
Non-electrified	0	0	0	0	0
Total	25999996	2928894	771.71	3658.61	1259.85

Table 3: Results summary of Scenario 2

Key Findings

- Number of new MG PV Hybrid = 385
- Number of new MG Hydro = 21
- Total Investment cost = 3658.61

Figure 3: Technology Map for Scenario 2

Figure 4: Population electrification rate for Scenario 2

Scenario 2 focuses more on grid expansion and thereby reducing the number of mini grids to be deployed. Compared to Scenario 1, it reduces the number of mini grids from 1158 to 406 and there by increases the number of connections to the grid.

4. DISCUSSION

The results demonstrate Zambia can achieve universal electricity access by 2030 through a combination of grid extension & densification, mini-grids and SHSs.

4.1 Insights and Implications

Scenario 1, which focuses on a more decentralized strategy where mini grids and SHSs will play a crucial role in electrifying low density areas. Taking this approach requires 1157 new mini grids, which is the most practical way to electrify remote communities where grid infrastructure is absent. This approach supports distributed generation, encourages private sector investment and strongly aligns with rural electrification objectives.

Scenario 2 focuses more on grid expansion with 70% of connections from grid extension and densification. It aligns to Zambia's aim of expanding and upgrading existing transmission infrastructure, tripling generation capacity and foster regional integration. However, this approach sees a higher investment cost of USD 3.66 billion and may imply longer implementation time.

4.2 Policy Recommendations and Opportunities

To expand access in remote and low densely populated provinces such as Western, Luapula and Mulching, Zambia should prioritize the deployment of mini grids and SHSs particularly in remote areas where grid extension costs are higher.

Private investment is essential in scaling up decentralized energy systems. However, high upfront costs and a lack of incentives tend to discourage participation. Zambia should scale up support mechanisms to enhance private sector engagement.

In areas where grid extension and densification are feasible, significant investment is required to strengthen the existing infrastructure. Upgrading transmission and distribution networks will increase system reliability and support load growth, particularly in peri-urban and high-demand rural areas.

Achieving universal access by 2030 will requires mobilizing significant capital. Zambia should explore blended finance instruments, green bonds, and concessional climate finance to supplement government funding.

4.3 Limitations

- Unavailability of updated data remains a challenge. This greatly impacts the result output as the model is only as good as the data inputs.
- The model does not capture already existing SHSs
- Projecting commercial demand remains a challenge.
- The model does not explore non Hybrid PV mini grids.

4.4 Areas for Future Work

- A more centralized and accessible energy data system
- More geo spatial analysis capacity building programs in energy planning institutions.

5. CONCLUSION

The study utilized the OnSSET tool to model least cost strategies to achieve Zambia's universal electricity access target by 2030. Two scenarios were explored, one prioritizing mini grid deployment while the other prioritizing grid extension, both revealing that a diversified mix of technologies is essential to close the access gap. Grid extension is prioritized in urban areas while mini grids and stand-alone SHSs dominate in low densely populated rural regions. This mixed technology strategy aligns closely with the goals of Mission 300, Vision 2030, the IRP and the National Energy Policy (NEP) 2019, all of which emphasize diversified generation, grid investment and private sector participation.

Additionally, OnSSET acts as a decision support tool that complements energy planning frameworks through evidence based spatial prioritization. It also exposes potential implementation gaps such as the need for centralized and updated geospatial data and better demand profiling.

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